

EARLY YOUNG CHILDREN FROM ALLERGIES DIFFERENCE AND TREATMENT OF JAUNDICE

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Abstract. The difference and treatment of jaundice from allergies in early young children, their parents turned to a specialist in pediatric infectious diseases with one complaint: the presence of prolonged jaundice in a newborn. the period with the subsequent formation of enzyme activity in a biochemical blood test.

Keywords: Allergy, jaundice, bilirubin, phototherapy, liver, skin color,

Purpose of work: It is customary to use the following values as standard indicators of the state of health of newborns and children in the first year of life:

- total bilirubin (TB) level - 0.5-20.5 $\mu\text{mol/l}$
- indicators of ALT (AlAT) and AST (AST) enzymes - up to 40 units / l
- level of alkaline phosphatase (ALP) - up to 350 units / l
- The dimensions of the liver and spleen below the edge of the rib cage are not palpable or 0.0 cm.

Materials and methods. Jaundice in the first 14 days of a baby's life is physiological or breastfeeding jaundice. A retrospective analysis of health outcomes was performed in 45 children with prolonged jaundice. The average duration of jaundice was 69.3 ± 24.6 days, the amount of total bilirubin reached 146.4 ± 17.4 $\mu\text{mol/l}$ at the time of discharge from the maternity ward, and 113.1 ± 42.3 $\mu\text{mol/l}$ during one month. remained at the level of l. l, that is, 7-5 times exceeded the norm. Complete normalization of bilirubin level and disappearance of jaundice was noted only up to the fifth month of life.

A characteristic feature of the dynamics of OB, ALT and AST indicators is that enzyme activity called hepatitis or liver inflammation appears against the background of a general tendency to normalize OB levels. And then the normal jaundice of a newborn takes on the characteristics of pathological prolonged jaundice. The duration of the increase in the level of enzymes is 7.5 ± 3.7 months, there is a direct relationship between the increase in transaminases and the beginning of the treatment of liver inflammation, in other words, pediatricians and parents treat jaundice for a long time. traditional methods that do not lead to success. The division into two groups was carried out according to the principle: children of group 1 (n. 29) received traditional treatment for jaundice for a long time up to 4-6 months, children in group 2 (n. 16). Combined treatment prescribed early with 1.5 -2 months. Patients in the compared groups

had the same initial parameters during the treatment: weight and height were within acceptable limits, the degree of increase in the size of the liver and spleen did not differ, the duration of jaundice was the same and. It was 70.9 ± 32.1 days in the 1st group, 68.6 ± 30.3 days in the 2nd group. Thus, almost all children with long-term jaundice later developed liver disease, in 100% of cases it was found that they had symptoms of TORCH infections and various variants, which did not positively "respond" to traditional methods of treatment.

The effectiveness indicators of early combined therapy aimed at eliminating jaundice in group 2 are as follows. Against the background of early combined treatment, the volume of the liver and spleen was significantly reduced in children of group 2, TB, ALT and AST indicators were normalized. The duration of treatment in group 2 was shorter than in group 1 (9.5 ± 2.6 months) and was 4.2 ± 1.03 months. Group 1 started full treatment late, which had a negative effect on the children's health and contributed to the long duration of the inflammatory process in the liver.

Result and discussion. As a result of research, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- 1) newborns with a long-term form of jaundice have a high risk of infection, which leads to the formation of hepatobiliary system disease in the form of an enlarged liver and spleen, increased ALT activity. and AST enzymes,
- 2) the risk of infection is observed in the form of mono-infection with a frequency of 51.7% in group 1 and 56.2% in group 2; mixed infection occurs in 48.3% and 43.8% of children, respectively. Most often, clinical manifestations of active cytomegalovirus infection (65.5% 1 and 75% 2), urogenital infections are detected in 31% and 12.5% of cases, respectively, herpes virus infections are detected in 13.8% and 37% of cases.
- 3) compared to children of group 1 who received traditional jaundice therapy for a long time, children of group 2 who started combined therapy early are in better condition and recover 2 times faster.

Summary. Thus, the conducted studies prove the feasibility of improving the treatment protocol for children with prolonged jaundice in the neonatal period. The value and advantage of the new method of treatment of long-lasting jaundice in young children is confirmed by the following facts: first, the treatment program was successfully tested in clinical practice and the effectiveness of therapy was proven by statistical methods of analysis; secondly, the long-term treatment regimen was tested in outpatient practice, which is timely and in demand in modern conditions.

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